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ПЛЮСЫ «ЦЕНЗУРЫ» И ЕЁ НЕОБХОДИМОСТЬ В СОЗДАНИИ КИНО

Аннотация: Данная статья посвящена анализу плюсов цензуры в кино и о его положительных сторонах. Идёт перечень плюсов отсутствия цензуры и его влияние на молодёжь

Ключевые слова: минусы, влияние, восточная кинематография, цензура, восточные принципы, культура, мораль, менталитет.

ADVANTAGES OF "CENSORSHIP" AND ITS NEED IN CREATING A MOVIE

Abstract: This article is devoted to the analysis of the advantages of censorship in cinema and its disadvantages. There is a list of disadvantages of lack of censorship and its impact on young people

Key words: advantages, impact, Eastern cinematography, censorship, Eastern principles, culture, morality, mentality.

Fundamentally opposite opinions regarding censorship have been expressed since the Enlightenment. Opposition on this issue also existed in German classical philosophy. Immanuel Kant stood for the freedom of expression of personal opinion, and Hegel believed that this freedom should be regulated by law and police measures.

Introducing various forms of censorship, state bodies, as a rule, motivate this with considerations of state security, the need to combat manifestations of extremism, the spread of harmful ideas, and counteract the moral decay of society. Voices in support of censorship are heard not only from government departments, but also from some public and political organizations, such as parties, political movements, the church.

On the other hand, according to critics, censorship does not really solve social problems, but only helps to hush up their existence. In addition, with the growth of the number of authors and the presence of the Internet, censorship becomes simply unrealistic.

Critics also point out that calls for the introduction of censorship often characterize the impotence of state and public organizations to solve certain social

problems. For example, critics of censorship believe that calls by religious organizations to introduce "moral censorship" in Russia in order to prevent the nation's morale from falling, in reality, reflect the inability of religious organizations to somehow influence the moral climate in society. A number of international organizations are fighting censorship, such as Reporters Without Borders.

Types of censorship

Despite the apparent simplicity of this phenomenon, there are many varieties of censorship. For their classification, criteria such as:

The nature of the information. According to this criterion, one can distinguish such types of censorship as moral, political, economic, commercial, ideological, religious and others.

participants in the process. This criterion takes into account the relationship between the regulator (censor), source and consumer of information. For example, if the source of information independently censors information, this is self-censorship. Pedagogical censorship controls what information the teacher gives to students, and departmental censorship monitors what information goes beyond the department. Corporate censorship provides a set of requirements that all employees who speak publicly on behalf of the company must comply with.

Implementation method. This criterion allows us to distinguish two main types of censorship: preventive (preliminary) and subsequent. The first type implies that the material is carefully checked before publication. In the second case, a censorship violation may be detected after publication, as a result of which punitive measures may be applied to the author.

The nature of the functioning. Censorship can be regular (carried out on an ongoing basis in accordance with certain rules) or spontaneous. The second option is often found in modern society. For example, if a published article causes a strong negative resonance in society, the editors may decide to remove or withdraw this article by publishing an apology or retraction.

Degree of institutionalization. This criterion shows how censorship is connected with state or social institutions.

Openness (publicity). This is an indicator of how much society is aware of the existence of a certain type of censorship. Allocate vowel (open) and latent (hidden) censorship. In this case, intermediate options are also possible.

Direction of activity. This criterion indicates for which consumer the information is censored. Internal censorship implies the protection of internal information from "leakage" to the outside, as well as control of its circulation within the system. The

external one makes sure that unwanted information from the outside does not get inside the system.

Mandatory. Censorship can be mandatory, recommending, allowing and approving.

legal status. If officially censorship is prohibited, but in fact exists, it is considered illegal. If it is enshrined in existing laws, then it is legitimate.

Subject. The subject (source of censorship) can be the state or government departments, the church, public institutions and organizations, society itself, a certain social group or individual.

Censorship in cinema is a system of control over film productions, the purpose of censorship is to control that things that can be harmful to society, the state, ideology, etc. do not appear on the big screen. There is state censorship in films in all countries, at the time of this survey, cinema censorship is absent only in Russia, except for public censorship, but public censorship cannot prohibit the release of a particular film, cannot cut scenes, public censorship can only discuss, condemn or approve.

In the 20th century, the most developed cinemas were in Russia (USSR), in the USA, and French cinema stood out noticeably. From the middle In the 80s of the 20th century, Soviet (Russian) cinema began to degrade sharply, like the whole country. Together with the collapse of the USSR, domestic cinema almost completely collapsed. But the censorship in films was completely removed. At first, this led to the fact that sheer blackness poured onto the screens. There were good films, but these are isolated cases and these films were not particularly noticeable.

It is known that cinema is censored in almost all countries. Very powerful censorship in the USA, where even in low-quality primitive films the presence of the US flag is mandatory. By the way, in China, where censorship is more ideological, scenes with the US flag are cut out of American films, from among those films that were generally allowed to be released in China. State censorship in the United States and China primarily protects such aspects of their societies as patriotism. Foreign films that can offend or somehow humiliate the citizens of countries are simply not allowed to be shown. Of course, those films that can harm domestic cinema in the US, China and some other countries in terms of earnings are not allowed to be rented. Films are either not skipped at all, or “dangerous” scenes are cut out of them.

LITERATURE

1. Алексеев Игнатий. Цензурный инфантилизм. Призывы ввести цензуру — попытка Церкви переложить свою работу на «власть» или признак отчаяния и паники? Портал-Credo.Ru (16 марта 2007). Дата обращения: 15 декабря 2020. Архивировано 12 мая 2021 года.
2. Горяева Т. М. Политическая цензура в СССР. 1917-1991. — 2. — М.: «Российская политическая энциклопедия» (РОССПЭН), 2009. — С. 8—9. — 407 с. — (История сталинизма). — 2000 экз. — ISBN 978-5-8243-1179-2., стр 118
3. Ольга Демидова. Дмитрий Полознев: «При Сталине девки были моложе». Журнал «Библиотечное дело». СПб.: Агентство Информ-Планета. Дата обращения: 1 января 2019. Архивировано 2 января 2019 года.